

Target CRM	REE (Nd, Pr, Dy, Tm)	Ni (Labeling element)	Al	Co, Mg, Mn, Si, Ti (Labeling element)	Cu	Cr	Sb - B (Inic base)	Li	B (Boatcase)	REE	Li	B / Boatcase	B / Boatcase	REE	Li	As							
application/waste flow	NiPrDy magnets in wind turbines	stainless steel in beams, columns, supports, roof structures, frames, cladding and roofing	Al alloys in windows, doors, cladding, roofing and structural components	Al alloys in windows, doors, cladding, roofing and structural components	wind turbine external cables	cables in buildings	flame retardant cable sheathing	flame retardant plastic flooring and roofing membranes	flame retardant EPS insulation (thermoelastic rigid panels)	flame retardant FRP insulation (thermoelastic rigid panels)	additive in concrete (prevent alkali-silica reaction)	preservative in wood	tiles and ceramics	tiles and ceramics	tiles and ceramics	glass wool	flat glass	flat glass	flat glass				
End treatment scenario without CRM recovery	no separation of magnets, magnets and/or in furnace fraction	steel is separated at source or in CDW recycling plant and used as casting scrap in a basic oxygen furnace (BOF) or remelted in an electric arc furnace (EAF) (see sorting according to alloy type)	Al is separated but not according to alloy type. Al scrap can only be downcycled to cast Al or end up as scrap surplus	Al is separated but not according to alloy type. Alloy elements are not functionally recycled	cables are not collected and left in the ground due to the high removal effort	collected scenario	removal of cable sheathing, incineration or energy recovery	incineration or energy recovery	incineration or energy recovery	incineration or energy recovery	recycled into aggregates for road construction or landfilling	incineration or energy recovery for possible shipping and production of particle board	landfilling or use as recycled aggregates for road construction etc.	landfilling or use as recycled aggregates for road construction etc.	landfilling or use as recycled aggregates for road construction etc.	landfilling	landfilling or use as aggregate substitute	landfilling or use as aggregate substitute	landfilling or use as aggregate substitute				
Putatively existing or potential end treatment scenario with CRM recovery	separation of magnets, treatment in a dedicated magnet recycling facility for material (short loop) or element (long loop) recovery (see requirements for element recovery below than for material recovery)	steel is separated at source according to alloy type (steel, stainless, etc.) and remelted in an electric arc furnace (EAF)	Al is separated at source and further sorted according to alloy type (series with laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) technology before remelting. Al scrap can be functionally recycled with alloy-specific counter input	Al is separated at source and further sorted according to alloy type (series with laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy (LIBS) technology before remelting. Alloy elements can be functionally recycled with alloy-specific counter input	cables are collected and sent to Cu recycling	cables are separated and sent to Cu recycling	removal of cable sheathing, chemical recycling methods for Sb recovery (Pillath et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2020; Spawes, 2020)	separation of membrane at source, chemical recycling methods for Sb recovery (Pillath et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2020; Spawes, 2020)	separation of EPS at source, chemical recycling methods for B recovery (Pillath et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2020; Spawes, 2020)	separation of FRP at source, chemical recycling methods for B recovery (Pillath et al., 2019; Gaudin et al., 2020; Spawes, 2020)	crushing of the concrete, separation into coarse gravel and the sand fraction, then the fine fraction further undergoes thermal treatment to generate clean sand and delipidated cementitious powder. Gravel and sand can replace aggregates in concrete and recycled cementitious powder can substitute cement. (Zheng et al., 2023) (Hypothetical scenario)	possibly leaching of borate salts from wood - chemical precipitation to recover from leachate (Hypothetical scenario, not confirmed)	tiles and ceramics are separated at source with high purity flow contamination with concrete etc. subsequently they undergo mechanical treatment (crushing etc.) and can be used as substitute for ceramic raw materials. CRM loop that functional use (Fu et al., 2024) (Hypothetical scenario)	tiles and ceramics are separated at source with high purity flow contamination with concrete etc. subsequently they undergo mechanical treatment (crushing etc.) and can be used as substitute for ceramic raw materials. CRM loop that functional use (Fu et al., 2024) (Hypothetical scenario)	tiles and ceramics are separated at source with high purity flow contamination with concrete etc. subsequently they undergo mechanical treatment (crushing etc.) and can be used as substitute for ceramic raw materials. CRM loop that functional use (Fu et al., 2024) (Hypothetical scenario)	glass wool is separated at source and recycled	flat glass is separated at source with high purity flow contamination with plastics etc. followed by flat glass recycling/hotmelting with functional use of the CRMs (Hypothetical scenario)	flat glass is separated at source with high purity flow contamination with plastics etc. followed by flat glass recycling/hotmelting with functional use of the CRMs (Hypothetical scenario)	flat glass is separated at source with high purity flow contamination with plastics etc. followed by flat glass recycling/hotmelting with functional use of the CRMs (Hypothetical scenario)				
5.4	Recycling conflicts with hazardous substances	How to evaluate the criteria?	No	No	No	No	Typically, ATO is added in combination with halogenated (mainly brominated) flame retardants. Some halogenated flame retardants are considered as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and are prohibited or restricted under the POP Regulation. The mechanical recycling of brominated plastics is prohibited due to the hazardous molecules that are generated during the process (Bilal et al., 2024; Gaudin et al., 2020). However, this is not a conflict for recycling, but removal of Br could also facilitate Sb recovery. If BFR-containing plastics are sorted and Br and Sb are enriched, this enables the recovery of Sb. According to the CLP-Regulation, waste is hazardous through if the concentration of ATO is >0.1% (L-Sb of 0.08%) (Pillath et al., 2020; CLP-Regulation (EC) 1272/2008).	Typically, ATO is added in combination with halogenated (mainly brominated) flame retardants. Some halogenated flame retardants are considered as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and are prohibited or restricted under the POP Regulation. The mechanical recycling of brominated plastics is prohibited due to the hazardous molecules that are generated during the process (Bilal et al., 2024; Gaudin et al., 2020). However, this is not a conflict for recycling, but removal of Br could also facilitate Sb recovery. If BFR-containing plastics are sorted and Br and Sb are enriched, this enables the recovery of Sb. According to the CLP-Regulation, waste is hazardous through if the concentration of ATO is >0.1% (L-Sb of 0.08%) (Pillath et al., 2020; CLP-Regulation (EC) 1272/2008).	Typically, ATO is added in combination with halogenated (mainly brominated) flame retardants. Some halogenated flame retardants are considered as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and are prohibited or restricted under the POP Regulation. The mechanical recycling of brominated plastics is prohibited due to the hazardous molecules that are generated during the process (Bilal et al., 2024; Gaudin et al., 2020). However, this is not a conflict for recycling, but removal of Br could also facilitate Sb recovery. If BFR-containing plastics are sorted and Br and Sb are enriched, this enables the recovery of Sb. According to the CLP-Regulation, waste is hazardous through if the concentration of ATO is >0.1% (L-Sb of 0.08%) (Pillath et al., 2020; CLP-Regulation (EC) 1272/2008).	Typically, ATO is added in combination with halogenated (mainly brominated) flame retardants. Some halogenated flame retardants are considered as persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and are prohibited or restricted under the POP Regulation. The mechanical recycling of brominated plastics is prohibited due to the hazardous molecules that are generated during the process (Bilal et al., 2024; Gaudin et al., 2020). However, this is not a conflict for recycling, but removal of Br could also facilitate Sb recovery. If BFR-containing plastics are sorted and Br and Sb are enriched, this enables the recovery of Sb. According to the CLP-Regulation, waste is hazardous through if the concentration of ATO is >0.1% (L-Sb of 0.08%) (Pillath et al., 2020; CLP-Regulation (EC) 1272/2008).	No	Trace wood preservatives such as PCP, Indane, COP, chromates (V) (see analysis) (the use is prohibited or restricted by EU regulations and they are phasing out)	Lead, cadmium, chromium, barium (see Annex 5 table guide, n.d.)	Lead, cadmium, chromium, barium (see Annex 5 table guide, n.d.)	Lead, cadmium, chromium, barium (see Annex 5 table guide, n.d.)	No	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	As is a hazardous substance itself
5.5	Environmental impacts	What are the environmental impacts of the ZCRM in comparison with the primary CRM? Is there any implemented/standardized calculation pathway for environmental impact assessment?	Ex-ante LCA of magnet recycling. Recovered NdPr magnets have lower impacts than primary powder for almost all impact categories (van Niselen et al., 2024).	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (leaving up to 70% energy) (Aomatsu & Aomatsu, 2019; Eufic, n.d.)	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (leaving up to 70% energy) (Aomatsu & Aomatsu, 2019; Eufic, n.d.)	Energy and chemical requirements for recycling are much lower than for primary production (leaving up to 80% energy) (Aomatsu & Aomatsu, 2019; Eufic, n.d.)	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Most likely no environmental benefits of recycling boron concrete	Most likely no environmental benefits of borate recycling from wood	Unknown	Unknown	Unknown	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).	Environmental benefits of glass recycling are widely recognized and accepted. It is one of the most prominent ways to reduce energy consumption and CO2 emissions from glass manufacturing (Eles for Europe, 2024).				
6.1	Recovery targets	Are there material or element specific recovery targets?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes			
6.2	Removal requirements	Are there any removal requirements related to the CRM containing application?	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive	Nothing besides the requirement for separate collection in the Waste Framework Directive				
6.3	Legal incentives	Are there any legal incentives for the recovery of the CRM such as special facilities in application, permission or registration processes?	If considered as strategic project under the CRMA Act, projects can benefit from streamlined and predictable permitting procedures and support in gaining access to finance. Furthermore, the requirement for a recycled content in permanent magnets in the CRMA Act can act as an incentive for recycling projects.	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No				
6.4	End-of-waste criteria	Are there established end-of-waste criteria for ZCRM?	There are no end-of-waste criteria for permanent magnet waste/concrete/brick yet.	Metal Scrap Regulation	Metal Scrap Regulation	Metal Scrap Regulation	Copper Scrap Regulation	Copper Scrap Regulation	Technical Proposal (Pillath et al., 2024) The proposed criteria include requirements on input material and the inclusion of hazardous plastic waste unless it can be treated to not be classified as hazardous under the CLP-Regulation.	Technical Proposal (Pillath et al., 2024) The proposed criteria include requirements on input material and the inclusion of hazardous plastic waste unless it can be treated to not be classified as hazardous under the CLP-Regulation.	Technical Proposal (Pillath et al., 2024) The proposed criteria include requirements on input material and the inclusion of hazardous plastic waste unless it can be treated to not be classified as hazardous under the CLP-Regulation.	Technical Proposal (Pillath et al., 2024) The proposed criteria include requirements on input material and the inclusion of hazardous plastic waste unless it can be treated to not be classified as hazardous under the CLP-Regulation.	No	No	No	No	No	Glass Cullet Regulation	Glass Cullet Regulation	Glass Cullet Regulation			

